

Increased resistance to abiotic stress in *Penaeus vannamei* postlarvae following chronic treatment with phloroglucinol

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ABSTRACT

In this study we investigated if the exposure to phloroglucinol increases *P. vannamei* postlarvae resistance against abiotic stressors. FG showed toxicity from 10 μ M after 24 hours exposure but when exposure duration was reduced to 2 hours no mortality was detected in concentrations up to 300 μ M. FG administered acutely, in a single dose, appears to be ineffective to protect postlarvae against ammonia. On the contrary, when PG was administered chronically as seven sublethal treatments spaced in time, increased resistance to abiotic stressors was detected. However, after 10 days of recovery animals were still stressed and weight and ammonia resistance was lower in PG-treated animals ($p < 0.05$). Interestingly, survival in salinity stress test (SST) was higher compared to control. After 20 days PG-treated animals had similar weight compared to control. Resistance to ammonia and SST was also higher in treated animals.

INTRODUCTION

Penaeus vannamei is the most cultured species representing about 80% of shrimp production globally (Dugassa & Gaetan, 2018). Demand for shrimp has grown with the increase in demand for animal-based protein. In response, annual global aquaculture production of shrimp has grown from 3.5 ton in 2009 to 6.0 in 2018 (FAO, 2018). Alongside with shrimp culture intensification raises the incidence of infectious diseases. Mainly as a result of farming under stressful environmental conditions where a weakened host immunity increases susceptibility to pathogens. Eco-friendly alternatives to prevent and overcome outbreaks in shrimp industry are needed. Recent findings highlight the capacity of shrimp immune system to be primed and to elicit stronger responses able to protect against stressors. Phloroglucinol, a phlorotannin commonly found in brown algae and plants with a wide range of applications in the industry, induce cross-tolerance towards pathogens and abiotic stress in shrimp. Phloroglucinol pro-oxidant activity was associated to Hsp70 induction, which mediated the expression of core immune genes as proPO in *Artemia* (Kumar *et al.*, 2018).

METHODS

Toxicity. Phloroglucinol toxicity towards *P. vannamei* postlarvae was investigated following two approaches, acute or chronic based on the time of exposure to the substance. Shortly, for acute testing animals were exposed for 2h, subsequently thoroughly washed with seawater to remove the compound and placed in clean seawater. Then, survival was recorded after 24 hours. Additionally, we tested for continuous exposure to FG, in this case postlarvae were exposed to phloroglucinol for 24 hours and survival registered at this point.

Acute exposure. Postlarvae 5 were collected from rearing tanks and transferred to 1 L seawater glass containers at 20 animals each. Animals were exposed to 10, 50, 100, 150, 250 y 300 μ M phloroglucinol for 2 hours. Then larvae were extensively washed with clean seawater to remove the compound. After 2 hours of recovery, postlarvae were challenged with ammonia LD50. Survival was recorded after 24 hours. Immobile animals which showed no reaction to mechanical stimuli were considered dead.

Chronic exposure. *P. vannamei* PL5 were stock in two 500L flat-bottom plastic tanks with 5000 animals each. Postlarvae were acclimatized for 2 days. Rearing conditions were 35 ppt seawater, 28-31 °C, pH 7.7-8.1 and dissolved oxygen above 6.2 mg.L⁻¹. Animals were exposed to 7 treatments of 2 μ M phloroglucinol for 24h every 3 days. Treatment period lasted 18 days with phloroglucinol being added at days 0, 3, 6, 9, 12, 15 and 18 from the start of the experiment. Rearing water was exchanged to completely remove the compound. After 10- and 20-days of recovery samples were collected to evaluate growth parameters (weight and length), resistance to ammonia and salinity stress. Animals were sampled at stages PL7, PL35 and PL55 at 0, 28 or 48 days from the start of the experiment.

Salinity stress test. The salinity stress test (SST) is a widely accepted index of postlarvae (PL) quality, either at the end of experimental treatments or to predict performance during stocking and grow-out (Palacios & Racotta, 2007). The experiments consisted of groups of 10 animals exposed to decreased salinity for 30 min or 1 hour, then animals were transferred back to 34 ppt seawater and after 30 minutes of recovery survival was recorded.

Ammonia toxicity assay. Ammonia toxicity tests were conducted following the procedure proposed by De Lourdes Cobo *et al.* (2014) with slight modifications. Briefly, animals were exposed to an ammonia mean lethal dose previously determined and survival was verified during the assay at specified intervals: 6, 12, 24, 48 hours.

RESULTS

Figura 1. Main findings. A, PG toxicity after 24 hours-exposure; B, PG toxicity after 2 hours-exposure. C, acute protection assay against ammonia; D & E, weight and SST after 10 days of recovery respectively. F & G, weight and SST after 20 days of recovery respectively.

RESULTS

Figura 1. Main findings

TIME	Group x Recovery (days)			
	C10	PG10	C20	PG20
6h	31 ^a	21 ^b	32 ^b	39 ^a
12h	14	10	16 ^b	26 ^a
24h	4	0	3 ^a	10 ^a
36h	0	0	2	3
48h	0	0	0	1

Tabla 1: Ammonia toxicity after 10 and 20 days of recovery

CONCLUSIONS

Phloroglucinol is a polyphenol that may be valuable in increasing the resistance of *P. vannamei* postlarvae against stress. Our findings suggest this compound is ineffective in unique dose. Specifically, it requires a prolonged stimulation through several sublethal doses to achieve the effect. However, phloroglucinol shows some toxicity during prolonged exposure which could impair shrimp growth. Dose and frequency of application must be optimized in order to be applied at hatchery scale. Our results provide new information on the use of phloroglucinol as an immunostimulant in shrimp farming.